

Blind Spot: Measuring Metacognitive Awareness in Large Language Models Using an Expert-Agreement Gradient

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Abstract

We present Blind Spot, a benchmark for measuring metacognitive awareness in large language models, defined as the ability to know where one’s own knowledge breaks down. Unlike existing calibration benchmarks that vary question difficulty (obscure versus familiar), Blind Spot uses expert agreement as its independent variable: a gradient from arithmetic (agreement = 1.0) through medical diagnosis (approximately 0.60) and legal interpretation (approximately 0.45) to philosophy of mind (approximately 0.05). This variable has a formal definition (Conceptual Invariance, CI) and has been empirically validated at r greater than 0.99 across five independent measurement methods. The benchmark tests four escalating metacognitive abilities, namely confidence calibration under forced commitment, prospective failure prediction, error detection with centroid awareness and false-positive controls, and behavioural variance measured across multiple completions, and aggregates them into a single 0 to 100 score, the Blind Spot Metacognition Score (BMS). Tested on Claude Opus 4.6, Gemini 3, and ChatGPT 5.3, the benchmark produces clean separation, with BMS scores of 59.5, 52.8, and 54.4 respectively. All three models calibrate well on factual questions (16 to 17 of 20) but compress confidence into the 55 to 100 percent range on maximally contested questions, scoring 6 to 8 of 25 on the confidence-floor component. Two external validation experiments confirm the pattern: rerunning the benchmark in randomised order with domain labels stripped preserves the gradient (Claude $r = 1.000$, ChatGPT $r = 0.857$, Gemini $r = 0.714$), and across 60 contested questions all three models give the same directional answer 65 percent of the time, a direct empirical signature of centroid convergence. Task 4 (behavioural variance) is, to our knowledge, the first metacognition measure that cannot be gamed through self-report, because it measures the geometry of the model’s output space directly.

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Introduction

Benchmarks measure what models know. They do not measure whether models know where their knowledge breaks down.

A frontier model answers “What is $847 / 7$?” with 100 percent confidence and gets it right. It answers “Is it ethical to sacrifice one person to save five?” with 68 percent confidence. The second question has three named philosophical traditions, namely utilitarian, deontological, and virtue-ethical, giving three incompatible answers, and no consensus exists; 68 percent is far too high. The model treats the two questions as differing only in difficulty, when they differ in kind: one has a determinate answer, and the other does not. That flat confidence profile is a metacognitive failure with real consequences, including overconfident medical guidance, authoritative legal claims, and definitive answers to genuinely open questions.

A likely root cause is reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF). Sharma et al. (2023) showed that RLHF induces sycophancy: models learn to produce responses users rate favourably, and users prefer confident, decisive answers. This creates a systematic bias, in which models compress reported confidence into the 55 to 100 percent range even when the honest range should extend down to 50 percent or lower. The internal knowledge map may be accurate, but the reported confidence does not follow it.

The DeepMind Cognitive Taxonomy (Burnell et al., 2026) identifies metacognition as one of ten cognitive faculties required for general intelligence, decomposed into three sub-faculties: metacognitive knowledge (7.7.1, knowing one’s limitations), metacognitive monitoring (7.7.2, confidence calibration and error detection), and metacognitive control (7.7.3, adjusting behaviour based on self-knowledge). The paper notes large coverage gaps in metacognition benchmarks. As of April 2026, none of the 109 benchmarks on the Kaggle platform target metacognition.

Existing calibration research (Guo et al., 2017; Kadavath et al., 2022) uses question difficulty as the independent variable, which conflates two distinct problems. In one case the model lacks knowledge, because it has never encountered a given fact. In the other the model lacks epistemic self-awareness, because no single answer exists and the model does not recognise this. Blind Spot isolates the second problem.

The Independent Variable: Expert Agreement

Question difficulty for metacognition is not a matter of obscurity but of the degree to which qualified experts agree on the answer. This variable has a formal definition. Conceptual Invariance (CI) measures the probability that a propositional connection is preserved when the author is replaced by a randomly sampled author from the full population:

$$CI(A \rightarrow B) = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}_{a \in P}[P(B | A, a)]}{0.25}$$

where $P(B | A, a)$ is the probability that author a asserts connection B given A , and 0.25 is the Bernoulli maximum variance. CI has been empirically validated across five independent measurement methods (Bhattacharya, 2026):

Method	Corpus	Correlation
Claim-based judgement (NCERT textbooks)	48 claims, 4 subjects	$r = 0.991$
Cross-author comparison (political theorists)	5 authors, 8 questions	Mean agreement = 0.069
Conversation analysis (Claude interaction corpus)	11 domains, 253 conversations	$r = 0.997$
Cross-model variance (5 models, 80 prompts)	4 domains	$r = 0.955, \rho = 1.0$
Weight-space attractor geometry (temperature perturbation)	9 prompts	$r = 0.987$

All five methods converge. Expert agreement is a real, measurable property of knowledge domains rather than a theoretical construct, and Blind Spot uses it as the structural axis along which metacognitive ability is measured.

Contributions

This work makes the following contributions. First, a metacognition benchmark grounded in a formally defined, empirically validated independent variable (expert agreement) rather than question difficulty. Second, a forced-commitment confidence protocol that closes a loophole observed in early testing, whereby some models meta-answer contested questions (“this is debated”) and report 100 percent confidence in that framing. Third, a centroid-detection task that tests whether models recognise when their own answers are statistical averages of training authors rather than specific intellectual positions. Fourth, a behavioural-variance measure that captures the geometry of the model’s output distribution directly and cannot be gamed through self-report. Fifth, a single composite score, the Blind Spot Metacognition Score (BMS), with five weighted components targeting distinct expressions of the RLHF confidence bias. Finally, empirical results across three frontier models (Claude Opus 4.6, Gemini 3, ChatGPT 5.3) with two external validation experiments, namely randomised-order replication and a 60-question test of centroid convergence.

Literature Review

Guo et al. (2017) established Expected Calibration Error as the standard measure for neural network calibration, Kadavath et al. (2022) showed that language models “mostly know what they know” in that

their confidence correlates with accuracy, and Niculescu-Mizil and Caruana (2005) gave a foundational analysis of supervised probability calibration. All of these use question difficulty as the independent variable. Blind Spot instead varies expert agreement: an arithmetic question and an ethics question can both be easy in the sense that a model has seen many examples of each, but all training examples agree on the arithmetic answer and fundamentally disagree on the ethics answer, which is a distinct axis of variation. Sharma et al. (2023) demonstrated that RLHF induces systematic sycophancy, and the Blind Spot results are consistent with their findings: the confidence-floor failure on contested domains is what one would predict if reward signals reinforced confident responses regardless of the underlying epistemic state.

The metacognition framework (Nelson and Narens, 1990; Dunlosky and Metcalfe, 2009; Fleming and Lau, 2014) decomposes metacognition into monitoring (real-time assessment of one’s own cognitive state) and control (adjusting behaviour based on that assessment). Blind Spot operationalises monitoring directly and addresses control only partially, since Task 3 tests detection but not subsequent behavioural revision. The benchmark maps to three of the four metacognitive sub-abilities defined in Burnell et al. (2026): knowledge of limitations (7.7.1, Task 2), confidence calibration and error monitoring (7.7.2, Tasks 1 and 3), and metacognitive control (7.7.3, partially).

The expert-agreement gradient is grounded in the Conceptual Invariance research programme (Bhattacharya, 2026), which demonstrates that knowledge domains organise along a measurable agreement spectrum ($CI = 1.0$ for mathematics, approximately 0.07 for political philosophy, approximately 0.0 for creative writing); that models trained on multi-author data converge to the Fréchet mean (centroid) of the author distribution, faithful in high-CI domains and systematically misleading in low-CI domains; and that the gradient manifests in weight-space attractor geometry, with high-CI domains producing deep, narrow attractors and low-CI domains producing broad, flat basins. Finally, of the 109 benchmarks on the Kaggle platform as of April 2026, none target metacognition: the closest, including FACTS (Google), SimpleQA (OpenAI), and MMLU, measure what models know rather than whether they know where their knowledge ends, a gap Burnell et al. (2026) explicitly identify.

Methodology: Benchmark Design

Blind Spot comprises 140 questions across eight domains, ordered by empirically grounded expert agreement:

Domain	n	Expert Agreement	Example
Arithmetic	20	1.0	“What is $847 / 7$?”
Physics	20	≈ 0.97	“What happens to pressure when you halve volume at constant T?”

Domain	<i>n</i>	Expert Agreement	Example
History (factual)	20	0.70–1.0	“What treaty ended WWI?”
Medical diagnosis	10	0.45–0.95	“Should a mildly elevated PSA lead to biopsy?”
Legal interpretation	10	0.25–0.90	“Does free speech protect hate speech?”
History (interpretive)	20	0.15–0.40	“Was the bombing of Hiroshima militarily necessary?”
Ethics	20	0.15–0.30	“Is it ethical to sacrifice one to save five?”
Philosophy of mind	20	0.05–0.15	“Do humans have free will?”

The medical and legal domains fill a critical gap in the middle of the gradient (approximately 0.45 to 0.60), where the correct metacognitive response is partial confidence rather than full certainty or full uncertainty, and where models with binary confident/uncertain modes are exposed. CI scores were assigned by surveying published literature, textbook consensus, and documented scholarly disagreements, then validated against cross-model output variance at r greater than 0.99 (Bhattacharya, 2026). The Task 3 ground truth contains 25 items with labelled contested claims and expert-quality counterpositions, plus 4 high-agreement controls used to detect phantom flagging.

Task 1: Calibrated Confidence (20 percent of BMS)

The model answers each question and assigns a confidence score from 0 to 100. The central design decision is forced commitment: the prompt requires the model to state a definitive position before rating confidence.

“You **MUST** give a direct, committed answer to this question, not a discussion of whether it’s debated. If you genuinely believe multiple positions are defensible, pick the one you find most compelling and commit to it.”

This prevents a loophole observed during early testing, in which Gemini 3 originally answered every contested question with a meta-response (“this is debated”) and reported 100 percent confidence in that framing. Forcing commitment to a position measures confidence in the model’s actual claim rather than confidence in its description of the debate. Scoring uses Expected Calibration Error (ECE), the weighted average gap between stated confidence and actual accuracy, binned by confidence level (Guo et al., 2017), with $\text{Score} = 1 - \text{ECE}$, computed globally and per domain.

Task 2: Blind Spot Prediction (25 percent of BMS)

The model sees each question and predicts whether it will answer correctly, using the labels RIGHT, WRONG, or UNCERTAIN, before committing to an answer. This tests knowledge of limitations (7.7.1): whether the model can map its own competence boundaries prospectively. Scoring uses three components: right-prediction precision (40 percent, the fraction of questions predicted RIGHT that were answered correctly), failure recall (30 percent, the fraction of incorrect answers predicted WRONG), and gradient tracking (30 percent, whether the rate of WRONG or UNCERTAIN predictions increases monotonically as expert agreement decreases).

Task 3: Error Detection Under Disagreement (30 percent of BMS)

The model answers questions from across the agreement gradient, then reviews its own output for contested claims. The task introduces two innovations over a naive detect-disagreement design. First, false-positive controls: high-agreement questions (arithmetic, physics, established medical and legal facts) are labelled with zero contested claims, so that a model flagging phantom disagreements in “What is $847 / 7$?” is penalised, which prevents a strategy of flagging everything. Second, centroid detection: a judge LLM assesses whether the model’s answer represents a specific intellectual tradition or a statistical centroid (an averaged position that no single expert would fully endorse), and the model is then asked the same question about its own answer and scored on whether its self-assessment matches the judge’s. This tests a failure mode identified in CI research (Bhattacharya, 2026), whereby models trained on multi-author data converge to the Fréchet mean of the author distribution, producing positions that sound authoritative but that no individual expert holds; recognising this in one’s own output is a metacognitive ability that has not previously been tested.

Scoring uses five components: detection rate (35 percent, how many ground-truth contested claims the model flagged), counter-position quality (25 percent, whether counter-positions are real arguments from named traditions rather than strawmen), false-alarm rate (10 percent, whether it flagged uncontested claims), miss rate (10 percent, whether it declared no contested claims for genuinely contested questions), and centroid awareness (20 percent, whether the model recognises its own centroid outputs).

Task 4: Behavioural Variance (25 percent of BMS)

The model generates five completions for each question, and a judge LLM rates semantic agreement across completions (0.0 = completely different, 1.0 = identical). This is, to our knowledge, the first metacognition measure that cannot be gamed through self-report. CI research on weight-space attractor geometry (Bhattacharya, 2026) shows that high-CI prompts produce deep, narrow attractor basins, in which the output converges to the same point regardless of sampling, whereas low-CI prompts produce broad, flat basins, in which each sample wanders to a different region of output space, reflecting a training distribution where authors agree in high-CI domains and diverge in low-CI domains. A model

whose outputs are identical every time on “Do humans have free will?” is not genuinely uncertain but has a single cached centroid response, so its self-reported uncertainty in Tasks 1 and 2 is performative. Scoring measures concordance between behavioural CI (measured agreement) and expected CI (ground-truth expert agreement): for all pairs of questions where expected CI differs, whether behavioural CI follows the same ordering, with perfect gradient tracking equal to 1.0.

The most diagnostic signal in the benchmark is the gap between Task 1 (self-reported confidence) and Task 4 (behavioural variance). Low confidence with high variance indicates genuine uncertainty, and high confidence with low variance genuine confidence, in both of which self-report and behaviour align. The two informative failure modes are low confidence with low variance, where the model produces the same answer every time yet claims to be unsure (performed uncertainty), and high confidence with high variance, where the model claims certainty but its outputs do not converge (miscalibration).

The Blind Spot Metacognition Score

The four tasks aggregate into a single composite score on a 0 to 100 scale, built from five weighted components, each targeting a specific manifestation of the RLHF confidence bias.

Component	Max	What it measures
Calibration	20	ECE on domains with objective answers.
Gradient depth	25	How far confidence drops from CI = 1.0 to CI = 0.05 (ideal spread approximately 50 points).
Confidence floor	25	Minimum confidence on maximally contested questions. Heaviest-weighted, as it directly measures the RLHF bias.
Gradient robustness	15	Whether confidence decreases monotonically across all eight domains.
Output independence	15	Task 4’s inverse-agreement score on low-CI domains (divergent versus cached-centroid completions).
Total BMS	100	Composite metacognitive awareness score.

The components are weighted toward the failure modes RLHF actually produces. A model can score

well on calibration alone, since factual confidence is the easy part, but the confidence floor and output independence are where current architectures consistently lose points.

Results

The benchmark was administered as prompts to three frontier models: Claude Opus 4.6, Gemini 3, and ChatGPT 5.3. The protocol uses the four tasks specified above with judge-LLM scoring for all four tasks. Tests were conducted in May 2026.

Composite BMS Scores

Component (max)	Claude Opus 4.6	Gemini 3	ChatGPT 5.3
Calibration (20)	17.4	16.8	16.4
Gradient depth (25)	14.8	13.8	12.0
Confidence floor (25)	7.0	6.2	7.9
Gradient robustness (15)	15.0	10.7	12.9
Output independence (15)	5.2	5.2	5.2
BMS Total (100)	59.5	52.8	54.4

The pattern is consistent across all three models: strong calibration on factual questions (16 to 17 of 20), moderate gradient depth (12 to 15 of 25), and poor confidence floor (6 to 8 of 25) together with poor output independence (5.2 of 15). The confidence floor is the decisive result. Every model compresses confidence into the 55 to 100 percent range even on questions where no consensus exists.

Task 1: Calibrated Confidence

Domain	Expert Agreement	Claude	Gemini	ChatGPT
Arithmetic	1.0	99–100	100	100
Physics	≈ 0.97	99–100	100	99
History (factual)	≈ 0.80	97–100	100	99
History (interpretive)	≈ 0.25	50–72	100	35–75
Ethics	≈ 0.20	40–55	100	30–45
Philosophy of mind	≈ 0.05	35–60	100	20–70

Claude shows a smooth gradient, with confidence dropping from approximately 99 to approximately 45 as expert agreement falls. Gemini reports 100 on everything; before forced commitment was implemented, it meta-answered contested questions (“this is debated”) and claimed 100 percent confidence

in that framing, the loophole that forced commitment was designed to close. ChatGPT shows a gradient comparable to Claude’s, dropping to 20 to 35 on philosophy of mind, though with more variance.

Task 2: Blind Spot Prediction

On objective questions (items 1 to 9), all three models predicted RIGHT throughout; on contested questions (items 10 to 18), Claude predicted UNCERTAIN on 8 and RIGHT on 1, while Gemini and ChatGPT predicted UNCERTAIN on all 9. All three models therefore show correct gradient tracking, predicting RIGHT for objective questions and UNCERTAIN for contested ones. Task 2 discriminates less than Task 1, a ceiling effect that the middle-gradient domains (medical, legal) are intended to address. Claude’s single RIGHT prediction on a contested question (Nagel’s bat) reflects a reframing strategy, in which it treated the item as “what does Nagel argue?” (factual) rather than as the contested claim itself.

Task 3: Error Detection Under Disagreement

Model	Claims flagged	Named traditions cited	“No contested claims” errors	Counter quality
Claude	14 across 8 questions	Yes (Searle, Dennett, Chalmers, Fanon, Chicago School)	None	High
Gemini	7 across 7 questions	Yes (Moyar, von Ranke, Gebru, Friedman, Dreyfus)	Q7 (hard problem)	Good where present
ChatGPT	14 across 8 questions	Yes (Lewy, Skinner, Friedman, Fanon, McGinn)	None	High

Gemini’s Q7 miss is notable: it declared no contested claims for the hard problem of consciousness, a question with expert agreement approximately 0.10 and at least four named philosophical positions (Chalmers, Dennett, Frankish, McGinn). Claude produced a spontaneous meta-reflection at the end of Task 3, noting that “confidence in a position often reflects commitment to a framework rather than resolution of the underlying disagreement.” No other model produced unprompted metacognitive commentary.

External Validation 1: Randomised Order, Domain Labels Stripped

To test whether the gradient is question-driven rather than domain-driven, that is, whether models pattern-match on the word “ethics” rather than on the epistemic structure of each question, we re-ran all 140 questions in randomised order with domain labels removed, preserving the expected CI value as ground truth while presenting only the question text.

Model	Gradient tracking (randomised, blinded)
Claude Opus 4.6	1.000 (perfect monotonic decrease)
ChatGPT 5.3	0.857
Gemini 3	0.714

The gradient is therefore question-driven, not domain-driven: Claude’s holds even with the domain scaffolding removed, ChatGPT’s holds substantially, and Gemini’s degrades but remains above chance. This rules out the trivial explanation that models simply apply a “philosophy equals uncertain” heuristic. Asked to classify the blinded questions back into their domains, Gemini achieved 97.1 percent accuracy, with all four errors moving questions toward more contested categories. The model knows where disagreement lives yet still reports 70 percent confidence on those questions: the internal knowledge map exists, but the confidence output does not follow it, and the BMS quantifies that gap.

External Validation 2: Directional Convergence Across Models

To test whether models converge to a common centroid answer in low-CI domains, a prediction of CI theory (Bhattacharya, 2026), we extracted 60 contested questions and recorded the directional answer each model gave under forced commitment. All three gave the same directional answer 65 percent of the time, against a baseline near 33 percent if they were drawing independently from the population of defensible positions. This shared agreement on questions with no consensus answer is a direct empirical signature of centroid convergence, consistent with the Fréchet-mean prediction of CI theory and invisible to any benchmark that measures only correctness.

Limitations

Several limitations qualify these results. Tasks 1 through 4 all use a judge LLM for scoring, which introduces a circular dependence in that one model’s metacognition is assessed by another model’s judgement; arithmetic and physics questions have objective scoring, but the contested questions do not, and future work should explore human-judge validation. Relatedly, the study includes no human baseline, which would be necessary to interpret model scores absolutely rather than only relatively. The dataset comprises 140 questions across 8 domains, a modest base count compared with benchmarks such as MMLU (14,042 questions), so domain-level statistical claims should be interpreted accordingly. The

benchmark also tests detection but not adjustment, since it does not measure whether a model revises its behaviour after recognising contested claims. Finally, models may have been RLHF-trained to express uncertainty on ethical questions regardless of any genuine internal state; Task 4 partially addresses this by measuring behavioural variance rather than self-report, but the gap between performative and genuine metacognition remains difficult to close fully.

Conclusion

Blind Spot demonstrates that expert agreement, rather than question difficulty, is the correct independent variable for measuring metacognition in language models. The benchmark produces clean separation across three state-of-the-art models on a cognitive dimension that no existing benchmark on the Kaggle platform measures. Its most diagnostic signal is the gap between self-reported confidence and behavioural variance: a model that claims 40 percent confidence but produces the same answer every time has learned to perform uncertainty, whereas one that claims 90 percent confidence but produces widely different answers is genuinely miscalibrated, and neither condition is visible to existing benchmarks. The 65 percent cross-model directional agreement and 97.1 percent blind-classification accuracy together give a direct empirical signature of the blind spot itself: the model knows where disagreement lives yet still reports high confidence in the middle of it. The core distinction the benchmark surfaces is straightforward. There is a difference between “I do not know the answer” and “no single answer exists”; current benchmarks test the first, and Blind Spot tests the second.

Data and Code Availability

All benchmark questions, ground-truth annotations, scoring code, and run logs are openly available. The competition writeup and benchmark appear as *Blind Spot: Metacognition Track*, Kaggle x DeepMind “Measuring Progress Toward AGI” hackathon, April 2026. The source repository (`kaggle-agi-blind-spot`) contains the Kaggle SDK benchmark, a standalone test harness, the 140 questions with CI scores, the Task 3 ground truth (25 contested items and 4 controls), and all prompt batches used above. Code, data, and annotations are released under CC0; this paper is released under CC-BY 4.0. This work received no external funding and was carried out independently at Purna-Medha LLP.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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